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Investigation of Process Parameters for the Backward Extrusion of Arbitrary Shaped Tubes from Round Billets Using Finite Element Analysis

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Abstract: Process simulation for the backward extrusion of internally arbitrary shaped tubes from circular billets is presented in this paper. ABAQUS/Explicit finite element method has been used to analyze the problem. This kind of analysis has been done before using analytical solutions such as upper bound. However the FEM solution presented here is the first of its kind. Values of stress, strain and spatial velocity at different points in the deformation field were obtained. In order to observe the flow of the material during the process, grid deformations were also produced for the backward extrusion using the FEM package. Circular shape for the initial billet and the final tube's cross sections were considered and FEM solutions were given for each. The shapes considered were elliptical, rectangular, and circular shaped tubes and circular billets. The variation of extrusion load for the backward extrusion process was obtained for different values of reduction of area, aspect ratio and friction factor. Also, the effect of reduction of area, aspect ratio, and friction factor on velocity field and free surface configuration are investigated in this simulation and the results are shown in diagrams. The results produced from this work were compared with the theoretical and experimental results of other workers and good agreements were observed and some improvement in some of the results was also seen.

1-Introduction:

One of the important bulk forming processes which has a lot of applications is the backward extrusion which has been the subject of study of researchers for many years. This process is very useful for making shaped sections with closed ends or integrated parts which are difficult to produce by means of other processes. Bae, W. B. and Yang, D. Y. [1] gave an upper-bound method to determine the final-stage extrusion load and the deformed configuration for the three-dimensional backward extrusion of internally elliptic-shaped tubes from round billets. In another paper, Bae, W. B. and Yang, D. Y. [2] presented a simple kinematically admissible velocity field for the backward extrusion of internally circular-shaped tubes from arbitrarily-shaped billets. They carried out experiments with full-annealed aluminum alloy billets at room temperature using four circular-shaped punches.

Another new kinematically-admissible velocity field was proposed by Bae, W. B. and Yang, D. Y. [3] to determine the final-stage extrusion load and the average extruded height in the backward extrusion of internally non-axisymmetric tubes from round billets.

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Rong-Shean Lee and Chin-Tarn Kwan [4] presented a modified kinematically admissible velocity field for the backward extrusion of internally circular-shaped tubes from arbitrarily shaped billets. From the proposed velocity field, the upper-bound extrusion load and average extruded height for regular polygonal-shaped billets were determined with respect to the chosen parameters. A new upper-bound elemental method was proposed by Y. T. Lin and J. P. Wang [5] to improve the ineffectiveness of the upper bound elemental technique (UBET) for solving forging problems that are geometrically complex or need a forming simulation for predicting the profile of the free boundary.

An upper bound formula was developed to analyze the backward extrusion forging of regular polygon cup shaped components in a paper by Moshksar, M.M. and Ebrahimi, R. [6]. Guo, Y.M., Yokouchi, Y. and Nakanishi, K. [7] analyzed two and one way axisymmetric hot backward extrusion problems by a combined finite element method. A finite element simulation for the backward extrusion of internally hollow circular sections from polygonal billets was performed by Abrinia and Orangi, S.[8]. In this paper investigation of process parameters for the backward extrusion of arbitrary shaped tubes from round billets carried out using finite element approach.

2-FEM simulation

A finite element analysis is used to simulate the backward extrusion of billets with different cross sections using circular dies with various cross sections. The cross section considered for the billet was circle. The final internal cross sections of the tubes were elliptic, rectangular, and hexagonal which are in fact the shapes of the punches used in the process. Commercial pure aluminum (AA2024-O) was chosen as the working material. For elliptic, rectangular, and hexagonal tubes, the diameter of circular billet (blank) was 25 mm with a length of 25 mm. For the beginning of the process the distance between the punch and the billets was taken as 0.5 mm. The inside diameter of container in all cases was taken to 0.4 mm greater than the billet diameter. The material properties for the simulated models were assumed as follows:

For AA2024-O[1]

$$\bar{\sigma} = 292.77 * \bar{\varepsilon}^{0.15} (Mpa)$$

$$\rho = 2780(kg / m^3)[9]$$

$$E = 73.1(Gpa)[10]$$

$$\varepsilon = 0.33$$

$$\sigma_y = 78.5(Mpa)[11]$$

The reduction of area described as:

$$RA\% = \frac{a}{A}(100), a: \text{section area of punch, } A: \text{section area of billet}$$

Assumptions made in simulation were as follows:

- a) material property for container and die were modeled as perfectly rigid.
- b) Interaction: tangential behavior
- c) Boundary conditions: Container movement are constrained in all directions; punch movement is constrained in all directions except the vertical direction.

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- d) Type of element for the container modeled as discrete rigid:C3D8R
- e) Type of the element for punch modeled as analytical rigid:R3D4, A 4-node 3-D bilinear rigid quadrilateral
- f) Element type for billet modeled as deformable: C3D8R, An 8-node linear brick.
- g) Adaptive meshing was chosen.

For example, for circular billet –elliptical punch:

Details for elements are:

- 1. The upper face of billet which is in contact with punch is partitioned on the basis of elliptic shape.**
- 2. element shape: hexahedral, technique: sweep**
- 3. Number of nodes: 12116**
- 4. Number of elements: 10800**
- 5. 10800 Linear hexahedral elements of type C3D8R**
- 6. Element library: Explicit, 3d stress**
- 7. Geometric order: linear**
- 8. Using ALE adaptive mesh domain: remeshing sweep per element:800000, remeshing sweep per increment:3 , initial remeshing sweep value: 100,**
- 9. Element failure criteria: for all models, the optimum element size was obtained by trial and error until the worst aspect ratio: 3 are achieved.**

3-Results and Discussion:

3-1-Circular billet-elliptic punch

3-1-1- Extrusion load

Figure 1 shows the effect of area reduction on extrusion load for backward extrusion of internally elliptic-shaped tubes from round billets. The extrusion load increases with increasing reduction of area for a fixed aspect ratio and the given friction factor. FEM simulation method was compared with the experimental and theoretical values [1], good agreement being found .For reduction of area 36-49%, the extrusion loads have good coincidence to experimental loads. The maximum difference of simulation load in comparison to experimental load has been observed in 64% of area reduction.

The present simulations of extrusion load versus various aspect ratios in figure 2 are in good agreement with the experimental load values and theoretical predictions [1]. For aspect ratio 1 to 1.3 the simulation results are closer to experimental ones.

Figure 3 shows the simulation results of friction factor effect on extrusion load. For a given reduction of area and fixed aspect ratio, the extrusion load increases with enhancing the friction factor.

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3-1-2- Distribution of velocity and configuration of the free surface of the extruded billet

The simulation results for the velocity distribution of the extruded billet are shown in Figures 4 to 6 for different area reductions, aspect ratios, and friction factors, respectively. The effect of area reduction on the configuration of the free surface and velocity field contours of extruded billet for a given aspect ratio and the given friction factor are shown in figure 4.

Figure 5 show the effect of aspect ratio on the configuration of the free surface and velocity field contribution of extruded billet for a fixed area reduction and the given friction factor are shown.

In figure 6 are shown friction factor effect on the configuration of the free surface and velocity field of extruded billet for a given aspect ratio and the fixed area reduction. Diagrams of the velocity variables versus various area reductions, aspect ratios, and friction factors are shown in figures 7 to 9, respectively.

The diagram of velocity variables versus different area reduction for the identical conditions has been shown in figure 7-a, for reduction area less than 25% the velocity being seen to decrease with increasing area reductions and for area reduction RA=25% to 64%, velocity being seen to increase with increasing area reductions. The results of simulation for RA=25% to RA=49% have been compared with theoretical predictions and experimental test for velocity field [1] and good agreement has been obtained. Simulation results for grid deformation is observable in figure 7-b. Because of thinning of work piece wall in RA=64%, the material flows toward punch and distorted excessively; therefore the material flow encounter problem.

In figure 8 the effect of aspect ratio on velocity has been shown. The variable rates of velocities from A.R=1.25 to A.R=1.5 are trivial and from A.R=1.5 to A.R=1.75 the velocity has decreased. Analytical results are analogous to the results of ref.[1] that had been performed for A.R=1.25, A.R1.75.

In figure 9 the effect of friction factor on velocity field has been shown. Except $m=0.1$ to 0.2 for $m=0.2$ to 0.9 , there being found to be no appreciable difference between two cases.

3-2- Circular billet-rectangular punch results

3-2-1-Extrusion load

Figures10-13 shows the results of FEM simulation for internally rectangular sections from round billets. In figure 10 a graph of extrusion load versus reduction of area is given for the backward extrusion of internally rectangular sections from circular billets. Comparison of other theoretical and experimental results with the FEM simulation of the authors is also seen in this figure. Authors' results show better agreement with the experimental values at lower values of the reduction of area.

In figure 11 a graph of extrusion load versus aspect ratio is given for the backward extrusion of internally rectangular sections from circular billets. Authors' results show better agreement with the experimental values at lower values of aspect ratio.

In figure12 a graph of extrusion load variables V.S various friction factor for the backward extrusion simulation of internally rectangular sections from circular billets is shown. The extrusion load increases with increasing friction factor. Because with increasing friction

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factor the amount of friction force increases and this force enhances the total load required for performing process.

3-2-2-Velocity field distribution

For the same extrusion, the grid deformation and spatial velocity distribution at nodes are also given in figure 13. Starting from the initial stage of the extrusion process and going through to the end, 5 different stages are observed. The values of velocity distribution in the part are also shown for each stage. The velocity field is shown by three directional velocities, V1, V2 and V3. The magnified figure of one stage for contour distribution of V1, V2, V3 are shown in 13.I, 13.II and 13.III. V1 was greater at locations near to the punch corner than elsewhere and it is lowest at the center of free surface of extruded part(1). Also, V1 decreases from (1) to (2), nodes near the wall of container.

V2 was greater at locations (3), (4) and between these sections, V2 is lowest. V3 was greatest at (5) and decreases toward (6), work piece nodes near the container wall. From (7), near free surface of workpiece toward (8), nodes near container lower section, V3 decreases gradually. These results were not obtained by other methods in other references.

3-3- circular billet-hexagonal punch results

3-3-1-Extrusion load

Figure 14-17 show simulation results for backward extrusion of internally hexagonal sections from circular billets. In figure 14 a graph of extrusion load versus reduction of area is given for the backward extrusion of internally hexagonal sections from circular billets. In figure 15 a graph of extrusion load variables versus various friction factors for the backward extrusion simulation of internally hexagonal sections from circular billets is shown. The extrusion load increases with increasing friction factor.

3-3-2- Stress and strain contribution

For the same extrusion, the grid deformation and stress distribution are also given in figure 16. Starting from the initial stage of the extrusion process and going through to the end, 4 different stages are observed. The values of stress distribution in the part are also shown for each stage. A reduction of area of 49% was used for these simulations. It is illustrated that in which part of billet, the stress is greatest.

The results for the equivalent strain distribution for the backward extrusion of internally hexagon and externally circular shapes are shown in figure 17 for the 4 stages of the simulation. It could be seen that as expected the highest values occur at where the highest deformation is. As shown in stages, because of maximum deformation in surfaces of work piece which contacts with corner of punch, the plastic equivalent effective strain is greater than elsewhere. Also, in initial stage of the process, contours of strains are distributed in broad areas and gradually decreases through the end of process. Because, in initial stage, with increasing stress, the plastic area develops and includes larger region of billet, however, after material flow, the deformation area was fixed and strains confined in plastic areas. It should be mentioned that the results for the reference [2] are analytical and it could

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be seen that the simulations results by the authors shows good agreement with the analytical results.

4-Conclusions

Finite element simulation of the backward extrusion process was carried out for the internally elliptic, rectangular, and hexagonal and externally circular sections. The results for elliptic tubes obtained from 3-D simulation showed good agreement with previous work. The 3-D velocity field distribution and the free surface configurations obtained by the authors showed very good agreement with the experimental evidence and much improved over previous work. The 3-D simulation predictions for the extrusion force for lower reduction of areas were closer to experimental observations while for higher reductions they were further apart. Some results such as the velocity distribution during different stages of the extrusion process for rectangular tubes, other results such as, extrusion load graph, stress and strain distribution for hexagonal tubes were also obtained which were not given in the previous work.

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